

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

Ethyl methane sulfonate (EMS)- induced micromutation in a tall indica rice

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We induced mutations in quantitatively inherited traits of rice by presoaking

seeds of Dahar Nagra, a tall indica variety in 1% aqueous, freshly prepared, nonbuffered solution of EMS for 4, 6, and 8 h. Number of tillers per plant, panicle length, number of filled grains per panicle, 1000-grain weight, and yield per plant were reduced in the M₂ (Table 1) and M₃ (Table 2). Weight of 1,000 filled grains increased after EMS treatment.

Table 1. Mean and estimates of genetic parameters of 5 quantitative characters in the M₂ of Dahar Nagra after EMS treatment. Burdwan University Crop Research Farm, India.

Treatment	Mean of genetic character	Genotypic variance	Genotypic coefficient of variation (%)	Heritability (broad sense) percentage	Genetic advance (% of mean)
<i>Tillers (no./plant)</i>					
Control	21.38	0	0	0	0
4 h	17.38	1.048	5.8	15.4	1.82
6 h	14.11	3.255	12.7	24.2	12.94
8 h	12.94	5.377	17.9	27.1	19.19
<i>Panicle length (cm)</i>					
Control	28.81	0	0	0	0
4 h	25.33	0.090	1.1	5.5	0.57
6 h	23.66	0.564	3.1	18.4	2.79
8 h	23.07	0.998	4.3	22.8	4.26
<i>Filled grains (no./panicle)</i>					
Control	160.88	0	0	0	0
4 h	147.33	3.014	1.1	3.9	0.47
6 h	139.22	7.844	2.0	8.6	1.20
8 h	134.27	11.700	2.5	11.4	1.76
<i>Weight of 1000 filled grains (g)</i>					
Control	19.19	0	0	0	0
4 h	19.43	0.028	0.8	10.8	0.58
6 h	19.70	0.030	0.8	11.2	0.60
8 h	19.77	0.031	0.8	11.5	0.62
<i>Yield per plant (g)</i>					
Control	25.61	0	0	0	0
4 h	24.41	0.243	2.0	8.6	1.21
6 h	23.28	1.372	5.0	22.1	4.86
8 h	22.93	1.695	5.6	23.6	5.67

Table 2. Mean and estimates of genetic parameters of 5 quantitative characters in the M₃ of Dahar Nagra after EMS treatment. Burdwan University Crop Research Farm, India.

Treatment	Mean	Genotypic variance	Genotypic coefficient of variation (%)	Heritability (broad sense) percentage	Genetic advance (% of mean)
<i>Tillers (no./plant)</i>					
Control	18.61	0	0	0	0
4 h	15.55	0.711	5.4	20.1	4.99
6 h	13.55	1.700	9.5	26.1	10.10
8 h	13.22	3.433	14.0	29.3	15.60

continued on next page

Table 2 continued.

Treatment	Mean	Genotypic variance	Genotypic coefficient of variation (%)	Heritability (broad sense) percentage	Genetic advance (% of mean)
<i>Panicle length (cm)</i>					
Control	26.35	0	0	0	0
4 h	25.13	0.047	0.8	7.5	0.48
6 h	22.88	0.355	2.6	22.9	2.56
8 h	22.41	0.877	4.1	28.1	4.55
<i>Filled grains (no./panicle)</i>					
Control	160.38	0	0	0	0
4 h	146.94	10.970	2.2	15.7	1.83
6 h	129.72	23.833	3.7	21.9	3.62
8 h	126.16	24.435	3.9	22.1	3.78
<i>Weight of 1000 grains (g)</i>					
Control	19.16	0	0	0	0
4 h	19.32	0.006	0.4	3.0	0.14
6 h	19.53	0.016	0.6	7.1	0.35
8 h	19.58	0.018	0.6	7.8	0.39
<i>Yield per plant (g)</i>					
Control	24.62	0	0	0	0
4 h	22.97	0.724	3.7	13.6	2.81
6 h	22.31	1.340	5.1	18.6	4.59
8 h	22.01	2.145	6.6	22.3	6.46

EMS treatment induced genetic variability and genetic advance in the five quantitative traits. The longer the treatment, the higher the estimated genetic parameter. EMS treatment could be used to select improved plant types on the basis of induced polygenic variability, particularly in the M₃. $\mathcal{S}$

ERRATUM

IRRN 11:3 (Jun 1986) p. 25. On the item titled *Efficacy of slow-release N fertilizers on rice in coastal soils of Karnataka*, the author list was garbled. It should read: A.M. Krishnappa, K. Kenchaiah, B.N. Patil, Badrinath, K. Balakrishna Rao, and N.A. Janardhana Gowda. Mr. Badrinath's name was omitted. $\mathcal{S}$

Improved White Ponni released in Tamil Nadu

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Improved White Ponni has been released as a new variety for Tamil Nadu. It yields 300 kg/ha more than the local White Ponni but resembles it in all other characteristics.

Improved White Ponni, with 135-140 d maturity, is suitable for Sep-Oct and Jan-Feb plantings. At 130-135 cm tall, it is prone to lodging. Maximum yield was 6.3 t/ha. In 1984 data from 170 places in 11 districts, Improved White Ponni outyielded IR20 in 8 districts with an average 4.2 t/ha, 5.8% more than IR20 (Table 1). Average yield of

Improved White Ponni is 4.5 t/ha. Maximum yield potential is 9.2 t/ha. Improved White Ponni gives a straw yield of 7.4 t/ha (moisture-free basis)

compared to 4.5 t/ha for IR20 and 5.0 t/ha for CO 43.

The improved variety is moderately resistant to tungro (RTV), leaf

Table 1. Performance of Improved White Ponni in farmers' fields. Tamil Nadu, India.

District	Locations (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	
		Improved White Ponni	IR20
Thanjavur	39	3.3	2.2
Trichirappalli	7	5.8	4.6
Pudukkottai	8	3.9	3.6
Madurai	10	3.6	4.0
Ramanathapuram	2	3.0	3.7
Tirunelveli	24	4.1	2.9
Kanyakumari	4	4.1	4.0
Coimbatore	16	5.4	5.9
Salem	32	4.8	4.9
Dharmapuri	3	4.8	4.1
Chingleput	25	3.8	3.7
Total	170		
Mean		4.2	3.9

Table 2. Reaction^a of Improved White Ponni to diseases and insects. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	RTV		Leaf yellowing (field)	Bl		BB (field)	Sheath rot (field)	Grain discoloration (field)	Leaffolder (field)	Mite (field)	GLH (inoculated)
	Field	Inoculated		Field	Inoculated						
Improved White Ponni	3 (R)	5 (MR)	3-5 (MR)	5 (MR)	5 (MR)	3-5 (MR)	3 (R)	3 (R)	5-7 (MS)	5 (MR)	5 (MR)
IR20	8 (S)	9 (S)	7 (S)	7 (MS)	5-7 (MS)	3-5 (MR)	3 (R)	3 (R)	5 (MR)	5 (MR)	5 (MR)
CO 43	7 (S)	8 (S)	7 (S)	3 (R)	5 (MR)	3-5 (MR)	5-7 (MS)	5 (MS)	5 (MR)	5 (MR)	-

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.